

Composite Aircraft Certification

TASI'S MODULUS - DD CASE STUDY

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DD Case Study

DD and its
Advantages

Aircraft certification

Next steps and
Conclusions

Double-Double

BI-ANGLE LAMINATIONS

Double Double Bi-angled plies

$[\pm\Phi, \pm\Psi]_n$; $[+\Phi, +\Psi, -\Phi, -\Psi]_n$; $[+\Phi, +\Psi, -\Psi, -\Phi]_n$

- ▶ With $n=2$
minimal
coupling
- ▶ With $n \geq 4$
unperceived
coupling
- ▶ Balanced
- ▶ Symmetric
- ▶ Homogenized
- ▶ Ply-drops
- ▶ Optimization
tools

Tsai's Modulus

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^0 \\ K \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^0 \\ K \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [\alpha] & [\beta] \\ [\tilde{\beta}] & [\delta] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix}$$

- ▶ $A=D, B=[0]$
- ▶ Tsai's modulus = $Trace[Q] = Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 2Q_{66}$
- ▶ Tsai's Modulus = total material stiffness.

Tsai's Modulus & Transformations

Laminate	[0]	[0/90]	[$\pi/4$]	Soft1	Hard1	Soft2	Hard2	Tr (GPa)
% [0]	100	50	25	10	50	9	55	
% [± 45]	0	0	50	80	40	73	36	
% [90]	0	50	25	10	10	18	9	
IM6/epoxy	0.874	0.463	0.337	0.226	0.518	0.226	0.55	232
IM7/977-3	0.877	0.464	0.337	0.225	0.519	0.225	0.551	218
T300/5208	0.877	0.465	0.337	0.224	0.518	0.225	0.551	206
IM7/MTM45	0.897	0.471	0.337	0.213	0.523	0.217	0.557	195
T800/Cytec	0.888	0.472	0.335	0.211	0.518	0.216	0.552	183
IM7/8552	0.884	0.469	0.336	0.217	0.519	0.22	0.552	180
T800S/3900	0.898	0.476	0.335	0.206	0.521	0.212	0.555	168
T300/F934	0.883	0.472	0.335	0.211	0.517	0.216	0.55	168
T700 C-Ply 64	0.866	0.464	0.337	0.225	0.514	0.226	0.546	163
AS4/H3501	0.852	0.456	0.338	0.237	0.512	0.234	0.543	162
T650/epoxy	0.866	0.465	0.337	0.222	0.514	0.224	0.546	160
T4708/MR60H	0.897	0.475	0.335	0.206	0.521	0.212	0.555	158
T700/2510	0.877	0.47	0.336	0.215	0.515	0.219	0.548	144
AS4/MTM45	0.889	0.474	0.335	0.206	0.518	0.214	0.552	143
T700 C-Ply 55	0.869	0.466	0.337	0.222	0.515	0.224	0.547	139
Mean	0.880	0.468	0.336	0.218	0.517	0.221	0.550	
Coeff. Var. %	1.50	1.17	0.31	4.17	0.58	2.84	0.70	

$$\begin{matrix} Q_{11} \\ Q_{22} \\ Q_{12} \\ Q_{66} \\ Q_{16} \\ Q_{26} \end{matrix} = \begin{matrix} m^4 & n^4 & 2m^2n^2 & 4m^2n^2 \\ n^4 & m^4 & 2m^2n^2 & 4m^2n^2 \\ m^2n^2 & m^2n^2 & m^4+n^4 & -4m^2n^2 \\ m^2n^2 & m^2n^2 & -2m^2n^2 & (m^2-n^2)^2 \\ m^3n & -mn^3 & mn^3-m^3n & 2(mn^3-m^3n) \\ mn^3 & -m^3n & m^3n-mn^3 & 2(m^3n-mn^3) \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} Q_{xx} \\ Q_{yy} \\ Q_{xy} \\ Q_{ss} \end{matrix}$$

$m = \cos \theta, n = \sin \theta$

Data Extrapolation using Finite Fracture Mechanics Models

Extrapolation of notched data to a DD $[\pm 0/\pm 50]$ laminate using data identified from a DD $[\pm 15/\pm 60]$ laminate and comparison with experimentally determined plain and open-hole tension test results (Exp) and corresponding B-Basis values (B-values)

Tsai's Modulus is a Material Property

$$Tr = E_1 / 0.880$$

Laminate factors	E_x^0 / Tr	E_y^0 / Tr	G_{xy}^0 / Tr	ν_{xy}^0
Universal [0]	0.880	0.052	0.031	0.320
[0/90]	0.468	0.468	0.031	0.036
$[\pi/4]$	0.336	0.336	0.129	0.308
$[0_7/\pm 45_9/90]$	0.662	0.175	0.070	0.310
$[0_5/\pm 45_2/90]$	0.518	0.208	0.109	0.423
$[0_2/\pm 45/90]$	0.445	0.289	0.109	0.308
$[0/\pm 45_4/90]$	0.217	0.217	0.187	0.552
$[0/\pm 45]$	0.370	0.155	0.161	0.734
$[0/\pm 45/0]$	0.499	0.141	0.129	0.701
$[0/\pm 30]$	0.510	0.074	0.129	1.220
$[0/\pm 30/0]$	0.611	0.072	0.104	1.079
$[\pm 12.5]$	0.764	0.053	0.066	0.913

Aircraft Certification

Classical

- ▶ Production/Temp/Environmental/Static/Dynamic
- ▶ DOT/FAA/AR-03/19 Material Qualification
- ▶ DOT/FAA/AR-10/6
- ▶ FAA/AC-21/26A, FAA/AC23-20
- ▶ EASA AMC 20-29
- ▶ Composite Materials Handbook 17 AC20-107b, AR-96-111, AR-99/49, FAA/CT-86/39

Proposed

- ▶ Test matrix according to AR-03/19, production based on AC23-20
- ▶ Specimen testing of each material (fiber+epoxy), Basis A or Basis B data generation reduction of subsequent tests based on Tsai's modulus of specimens.
- ▶ Extrapolation of all other properties based on Tsai's Modulus and FFM models

Conclusions from testing

- ▶ Greener approach
- ▶ Fewer test specimens
- ▶ One to two orders of magnitude less in cost.
- ▶ Quicker and less wastage
- ▶ Confidence in data, better than 95%
- ▶ One material system's data can be used to fine tune structural performance.

Take home message: Tsai's Modulus and Double-Double

- ▶ The only technology that can reduce structural mass by 45% w.r.t. current LQL laminates, start thinking about how you'll use that 45% reduced mass...
- ▶ Many practical implications we have not touched on.

Some first aircraft parts in DD using ZeroVoid™ technology of NASHERO

Questions?

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Master envelope: radius normalized

From the ICCM23 Book on DD, by Prof. Stephen W. Tsai

Rating: Mat \equiv Lam

Scaling: one calibration test

Mat \rightarrow

CFRP-based Rqdius

DD-based Radius

From the ICCM23 Book on DD, by Prof. Stephen W. Tsai

